

Parental Cooperation with Teachers of Children with Dyslexia and Children Acquisition of Reading Competencies in Fako Division South West Region of Cameroon

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Abstract

Dyslexia are seen as a learning difficulty that primarily affects the skills involved in accurate and fluent word reading and spelling. Its characteristic features are difficulties in phonological awareness, verbal memory and verbal processing speed. This article focused on Parental cooperation with teachers of children with dyslexia and the Acquisition of Reading Competencies by Children Living with Dyslexia in Fako Division South West Region of Cameroon. The research problem focuses on the acquisition of Reading Competencies. Thus the main objectives was to ascertain the extent Parental cooperation with teachers of children with dyslexia and the Acquisition of Reading Competencies by Children Living with Dyslexia. A quasi -experimental design (a one group pretest posttest design) was used on a sample of 15 participants (comprised of 5 pupils, 5 teachers and 5parents). Data was collected using questionnaire and interview guides. The data collected was analyzed using the Pearson correlation index. A sample of 5 pupils, 5 teachers and 5 parents were examined using questionnaire and interview. Hypothesis shows that there is a significant, there is a positive significant relation between parental cooperation with school teachers and acquisition of reading competencies by children living with dyslexia as determined by the correlation index of = 0.716. From these result it was concluded that there is a significant relationship between Parental cooperation with teachers of children with dyslexia and the Acquisition of Reading Competencies by Children Living with Dyslexia. Consequently, a number of recommendations were made to policy makers of primary education on how to involve parents in the education of their children especially those with reading difficulties. Suggestions were also made for similar and further research to be undertaken in other towns and regions in Cameroon and in other parts of the world.

Keywords: Parental Cooperation, Teachers, Children, Dyslexia, Acquisition of Reading Competencies

Introduction

Schooling is an essential and indispensable need to live in the modern world. It guarantees a better life style. In the process of education, reading competencies are acquired. Everyone, including children living with dyslexia, needs reading competencies. Children who have this disability, especially those with reading difficulties often face problems in school. According to Garcia and Thornton (2014), involvement of the family in children's education helps to improve their test scores, social skills, reduced absenteeism, and increase in their self-esteem. This would highly contribute in reducing crime and poverty, something that our community and the world dread.

According to Cope, Eicher, Meng, Gibson, Hager, Lacadie and Gruen (2012), dyslexia affect the area of the brain that processes language. Children with dyslexia have normal intelligence, and usually have normal vision. That is why, they can succeed in school with tutoring or specialized educational programmes. Dyslexia is a disability, which affects the individual ability to read, write and spell. It is a learning disorder that involves difficulty in reading, due to the problem of identifying speech sounds, and learning how they relate to letters and words (decoding). Emotional support from parents also plays an important role in helping children with dyslexia.

Truduell (2012), said that the process of acquiring reading competencies are combined, observable and measurable knowledge, skills, abilities and personal attributes that contribute to enhance pupils' performance in school, lifelong learning sustainable development, especially in the area of reading. It is an individual ability to read, and spell successfully and efficiently. Reading competence is important to everyone in the society because it is a medium of communication skill, which enables an individual to express himself or herself in the home, in school, at job side, in church, in the market, or during meetings, just to name a few. Reading is fundamental to functioning in the society: it is a vital skill in finding a good job and discovering new things. It is fundamental in developing a good self-image. It is for this reason that the researcher sought to investigate the way dyslexic children's, reading abilities could be improved upon because these groups of persons face difficulties in reading, and this makes them drop out of school, and are sometimes looked down upon in the community. (Finn, & Panno, 1995).

Understanding The Concept of Dyslexia

According to Siegel (2006), dyslexia or reading disability, occurs when an individual has significant difficulty with speed and accuracy of word decoding. Comprehension of text and spelling are also affected. The diagnosis of dyslexia involves the use of reading text, but the continuum of the reading performance means that any cutoff point is arbitrary. The cognitive difficulties of dyslexia include problems with speech perception, recognizing and manipulating the basic sounds in a language, language memory, and learning the sounds of letters. Dyslexia is a neurological condition with a genetic basis. There are abnormalities in the brains of dyslexic individuals. There are also differences in the electro-physiological and structural characteristics of the brain of dyslexics. Dyslexia are stable, in that children identified as dyslexic are likely to continue to have reading difficulties throughout adolescence and adulthood (Siegel, 2006).

There is need for parents to be involved in the education of their children with Dyslexia at home. The focus has been that their activities towards reading at home improve their reading skills. The inclusive education according Dakar frame work of action (2000), insists on the right of education to all, by the year 2015 including children with dyslexia. It is important to know what the concept of dyslexia is, and the role that parents play in achieving this framework of action. In all our classrooms, we find dyslexic children and it is an issue in schools that must be addressed. According to British Dyslexia Association (2009), dyslexia is seen as a learning difficulty that primarily affects the skills involved in accurate and fluent word reading and spelling. Its characteristic features are difficulties in phonological awareness, verbal memory and verbal processing speed. Dyslexia occur across the range of intellectual abilities. It is best thought by a continuum, not a distinct category, and there is no clear-cut off points. Co-occurring difficulties may be seen as aspects of language, motor co-ordination, mental calculation and concentration.

Dyslexia is a learning disability in reading. Children with Dyslexia have trouble reading at a good pace and without mistakes. They may also have a hard time with reading comprehension, spelling and writing. There are two distinct kinds of reading difficulties involved with dyslexia: Acquired Dyslexia and Developmental dyslexia (Charolles, 2013). Acquired dyslexia refers to the disturbance of reading ability in a person who had previously learned to read normally, but who lost this ability as a result of brain damage due to infections in the brain. Developmental dyslexia concern difficulties associated with the process of learning to read.

Also, according to the World Federation of Neurology (1968), dyslexic children manifest difficulty in learning to read despite conventional instruction, adequate intelligence, and socio-cultural opportunity. It is dependent upon fundamental cognitive abilities which are frequently of constitutional origin (Critchley, 1970). In identifying dyslexic children, researchers and practitioners rule out children who have a sensory impairment (auditory deficit or non-corrected visual defect), an emotional disturbance, or neurological damage. Dyslexia are seen as an "unexpected" impairment of reading acquisition, for instances not connected with a visible cause.

To Lyon (1995), dyslexia is one of several distinct learning disabilities. It is a specific language-based disorder of constitutional origin characterized by difficulties in single word decoding, usually reflecting insufficient phonological processing. These difficulties in single word decoding are often unexpected in relation to age and other cognitive and academic abilities. They are not the result of generalized developmental disability or sensory impairment. The term "dyslexia" is often considered as being related to "specific reading disability (or retardation)" because the problem occurs without a general context of backwardness.

In addition, dyslexia a specific learning disability that is neurobiological in origin is characterized by difficulties with accurate and or fluent word recognition and by poor spelling and decoding abilities. These difficulties typically result from a deficit in the phonological component of language that is often unexpected in relation to other cognitive abilities, and the provision of effective classroom instruction. Secondary consequences may include problems in and personal organization, but these are not by themselves, markers of dyslexia. A good indication of the severity and persistence of dyslexic difficulties can be gained by examining how the individual responds or has responded to well-founded intervention (International Dyslexia Association, 2016).

There are so many causes of dyslexia. Dyslexia which is caused by difficulties in phonological processing, shows lacking sound with symbols in reading as the individual cannot decode letters. Another cause of dyslexia is cerebellar deficit, which is as a result of a problem in central processing linked to learning and automaticity, which make an individual find it difficult to read fluently. The magnocellular deficit is also another cause of dyslexia. This is dyslexia as a result of problems from visual or auditory deficits. (Pammer & Vidyasagar, 2005; Stein, 2001) an individual reads letters upside down.

To Ramus (2003), dyslexia can also have a genetic origin. This is because the brain of dyslexic children is organized differently and functions differently from normal children's brain, but it is unknown whether these are a cause or effect of the reading difficulty. A gene may have been identified that is responsible for dyslexia and if this gene is dominant, it would make dyslexia an inheritable condition. Dyslexia are more common in males than females. A number of reports suggest that dyslexia is more frequent in males than females ranging from 1.5:1 to 4.5:1 but it is unclear whether this observation is a result of selection factors and/or bias.

According to understood Team (2014-2020) there are seven types of dyslexia; phonological, peripheral, pure, hemianopia, negative, attention and surface dyslexia which will be seen and discussed below (National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke ,2013). Phonological dyslexia sufferers can read familiar words but have difficulty with unfamiliar words, such as invented pseudo-words. Phonological dyslexia is associated with lesions in the parts of the brain supplied with blood by the middle cerebral artery. The superior temporal lobe is often also involved. Furthermore, dyslexics compensate by overusing a front –brain region called Broca's area, which is associated with aspects of language and speech. The Linda Mood Phoneme Sequencing Program (LIPS) is used to treat phonological dyslexia. This system is based on a three-way sensory feedback process, using auditory, visual and oral skills to learn to recognize words and word patterns.

Peripheral dyslexia have been described as the one affecting the visual analysis of letters as a result of brain injury, hemianopia, a visual field loss on the left/right side of the vertical midline which is associated with this condition.

Pure dyslexia or phonologically based dyslexia also known as agnostic dyslexia, dyslexia without agraphia, and pure word blindness, is dyslexia due to difficulty in recognizing written sequences of letters (such as words), or sometimes even better. It is considered pure because it is not accompanied by other significant language related impairments. Hemianopia is another form of dyslexia commonly considered to derive from visual field loss due to damage to the primary visual cortex. Sufferers may complain of abnormally slow reading but are able to read individual words normally. This is the most common form of peripheral alexia, and the form with the best evidence of affective treatments. *Negative dyslexia:* Negative dyslexia is another form. In this case some letters, most commonly those at the beginning or left of a word are skipped or misread during reading. This alexia is associated with right parietal lesions. The use of prism glasses has been shown to mitigate this condition substantially (Dyslexia parent guide 2018-2019). *Attention dyslexia:* People with attention dyslexia complain of letter-crowding or migration, sometimes blending elements of two words into one. Sufferers read better when words are presented in isolation rather than flanked by other words and letters using a large magnifying glass may help mitigate this condition by words.

Surface dyslexia; is when words with regular pronunciation (highly consistent with their spelling example mint) are read more accurately than words with irregular pronunciation, such as colonel. Difficulty distinguishing homophones is a diagnostic used for some forms of surface dyslexia. This disorder is usually accompanied by surface agraphia and fluent aphasia. Acquired surface dyslexia arises when a previously literate person experiences brain damage, which results in pronunciation errors that indicate impairment of the lexical route. Children with Dyslexia often present the following characteristics: difficulties in learning to read, write, spell, and to do arithmetic. Difficulty in following oral and written instructions, cramped or illegible handwriting, and difficulty in staying on task. They are also easily distracted and have confusion in sequence of letters and symbols: e.g. (B and D), quiet and quiet, was and saw, 18 and 81, delayed spoken language. Confusion about directions in space, time, right and left, up, and down, north and south, yesterday and tomorrow. They demonstrate High level of frustration, difficulties retaining information and have more than average test taken anxiety.

According to Brazier (2017), there are so many signs and symptoms of dyslexia. In early child-hood, symptoms that correlate with a later diagnosis of dyslexia include. The following signs of dyslexia will be discussed below; delay in speech and phonological awareness, milestone reached later, concentration span, sequencing ideas and auto-immuno condition. Delay in speech and lack of phonological awareness: According to Mayo (2017), delayed onset of speech and a lack of phonological awareness, as well as being easily distracted by background noise are signs and symptoms of dyslexia. A common myth closely associates dyslexia with mirror writing and reading letters or words backwards. School difficulty in segmenting words into individual sounds or blending sounds when producing words, indicates reduced phonemic awareness. Difficulty with word retrieval or naming things is also another characteristic. Children with

dyslexia may exhibit signs of difficulty in identifying or generating rhyming words, or counting the number of syllables in words-both of which may depend on phonological awareness.

Also, to Siegel (2006), delayed language development may indicate that a child is at risk for dyslexia. Children who show delayed language development at three and four years of age are at risk for dyslexia, although many children who eventually become dyslexic have perfectly normal language development. Although not all children who have language disorder in early childhood become dyslexic, it is a very important indicator of a possible problem: these children should be monitored very carefully. Academic difficulties, especially difficulties with learning how to read, are a sign of dyslexia. Although children learn to read at different rates, if a child is having difficulty and performing significantly below his or her peers after a few months of reading instruction, this delay is a sign of potential problem and should not be ignored. School phobia and somatic complaints that appear on school days especially on Monday are a sign of possible learning disability (Siegel, 2006). People with dyslexia are commonly poor spellers, a feature sometimes called dys-orthographia or dysgraphia, which depends on orthographic coding. Problems persist into adolescence and adulthood, and may accompany difficulties with summarizing stories, memorisation, reading aloud, or learning foreign languages (Mayo, 2017).

Milestone reach letter: Children with dyslexia may learn to crawl, walk and ride a bicycle later than the majority of others.

Slow at learning sets of data at school, children with dyslexia may take longer to learn the letters of the alphabet and how they are pronounced. There may be problems remembering the days of the week, months of the year, and some arithmetic tables

Coordination: The child may seem clumsier than their peers. Catching a ball may be difficult. Poorer eye-hand coordination may be symptoms of other similar neurological conditions including dyspraxia. The child may confuse left and right. Again, the child may reverse letters and numbers without realizing it. Concentration Span; Children with dyslexia commonly find it hard to concentrate. Many adults say that after a few minutes of non-stop struggling, the child is mentally exhausted. A higher number of children with dyslexia also have attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) compared with the rest of the population. Sequencing ideas: When a person with dyslexia expresses a sequence of ideas, they seem illogical or unconnected.

Many claims have been advanced on how the competency level of dyslexic children can be enhanced. One of the ways is early detection. Early success in reading skills usually leads to later success in reading, while failing to read before the third or fourth year of schooling may be indicative of life-long reading problems. Thus, early detection is best made in early childhood or during the first year of school where the gap that separates the pupils at risk of reading failure and the pupils that are likely to be successful readers is small. Early detection alone however will not improve literacy levels unless the pupil receives appropriate early intervention before reading problems become entrenched (Velluntino, 2004).

Another way of enhancing reading competencies in children living with dyslexia is maximizing the chances for early identification of all at risk pupils. A test should be administered for early detection aimed to identify pupils at risk of dyslexia but making no attempt to diagnose dyslexic pupils. Tests administered at a young age are more inaccurate than tests administered at an older age. Early identification procedures need to be carried out with as many children as possible to maximize the chances for identification of all at risk pupils (Fuchs & Fuchs, 2001).

Nevertheless, according Wechsler (2004), determining a pupil's strengths and weaknesses, is also another way that can help dyslexic children to improve on their acquisition of reading competencies. Assessment tools that determine pupils' strengths and weaknesses in a range of areas can be used to design individual intervention strategies that target the identified weakness areas. These have greater benefit in an educational setting than a full psychometric test as they are relatively simple and quick screening methods that can be carried out by non-specialist staff.

Torgerson (2006), said early intervention can also help to enhance reading competencies in children living with dyslexia as early intervention is better than another form of teaching at risk or dyslexic readers. Early intervention, helps to solve specific needs of the individual, reduces the prevalence of dyslexia compared to individuals who did not receive intervention or support. Pupils who had early intervention compared to remediation at an older age show bigger gains in reading accuracy and fluency. It is also easier for them to catch up with their peers, and the long-term cost of their education is lower.

Also, instruction in phonological awareness and phonics at an early age has also been proven to enhance acquisition of reading competencies in children living with dyslexia. Timing issues with regard to preventive instruction have not been completely resolved by research, but at-risk pupils who had intervention in phonological awareness and phonics at an early age compared to remediation at an older age show bigger gains in reading accuracy and fluency. Also, teaching

phonological awareness significantly improves the reading of at risk or dyslexic pupils compared to an instruction that lacks attention to phonological awareness (Torgerson, 2006).

To Siegel (2006), educational accommodations include the use of computers, tape recorders, screen readers and speech recognition devices. Many dyslexics have illegible hand writing. The computer can be especially useful, particularly if touch typing skills are learned. Computers also have spell checking programmes, which are particularly useful because dyslexics have poor spellings. Tape recorders can be useful for the child to record his or her ideas, which can then be transcribed later. Tape recorders can also be used in classes and lectures because note taking skills can be a problem to dyslexic individuals. Screen readers are a device that reads aloud what is in the computer screen and can be very helpful for dyslexics. Books on tapes can also be helpful. Speech recognition devices and programmes are especially useful; the individual can talk into a microphone and see his or her words appear on the screen.

Any individual (child or adult) in whom a reading problem is suspected should receive an assessment. This assessment is available in schools and institutions of higher education. The assessment should involve a thorough measurement of reading, spelling and arithmetic skills. An intelligent test or IQ score is not necessary, as demonstrated by the latest research in the area. However, despite the literature, some jurisdiction still requires an IQ test. The state of affairs is unfortunate because there is either a long wait time for testing, sometimes as long as one to two years in many school districts, or parents or individuals must go to private psychologists to receive the testing, which is quite and out of the financial reach of many individuals (Siegel, 2006).

An evaluation of dyslexia should result in a written report (Worthington, 2019). This report should normally detail the kinds of information collected, which include information related to the family literacy history, any significant medical issues the child may have, prenatal and birth conditions, and preschool development, including language learning. The education history should include information on school attendance, tests administered and test scores. These scores should be stated as standard scores. Standard scores compare the learner to others of the same age or grade.

This material should provide the framework for the detailed evaluation of relative strengths and weaknesses across the various skill areas assessed, as well as the overall fit of all information with the typical profile of dyslexia for the child's age. This should lead to a tentative diagnosis that states that the child's ability to learn to read, write and spell does or does not appear to be related to dyslexia. The specific evidence that supports the diagnosis should be explained in the report (Worthington, 2019). According to International Dyslexia Association (2009), dyslexia evaluation comprises oral language skills, word recognition, decoding, spelling, phonological processing, automatic naming skills, reading comprehension and vocabulary knowledge.

Oral language skills: Oral language simply refers to our ability to listen to and understand speech as well as express our thoughts through speech. Oral language is made up of low-level skills, such as recognizing and making the sounds within our speech, and higher-level skills, such as getting meaning by listening to someone speak or creating sentences to express thoughts. Students with dyslexia typically have adequate higher-level language skills. Indicators of higher-level oral language skills include being able to understand an age-appropriate story and spoken directions, to carry on a conversation, and to understand and use words that are age appropriate. If a student has average higher-level oral language skills but much difficulty developing written language (reading and spelling) skills, the need for evaluation for dyslexia is recommended.

Conceptualising Reading in the context of Children with dyslexia

Reading is a mandatory skill to be a functional member in today's society (Høien, Lundberg, 2000). Modern society relies heavily on the skill to get written information, whether it is for leisure or work. Schooling depends on the skill, as reading is the foundation in which other subjects are based. Good reading skills can be seen as a corner stone for academic success (Høien, Lundberg, 2000). Language acquisition; how to listen, comprehend and speak, is naturally given to a child. The child receives it without any self-aware effort (Høien & Lundberg, 2000). Reading on the other hand, is a skill that has to be taught and learned (Rutter, 1978). In the most basic sense, reading is an ability to decode symbols in order to receive meaning (Nijakowska, 2010). But when dug deeper, reading is a complicated skill that builds on a number of decoding and comprehension processes (Rutter, 1978). It is important to note that the degree or level in which pupils experience reading problems vary from one pupil to another. Their areas of strengths and interests may be different too. It is therefore important for teachers to offer instructional support to each pupil depending on his/her strengths, interests and needs (Shaywitz, 2003).

Shaywitz and Shaywitz, 2003) as cited in Shaywitz, Morris and Shaywitz (2008). According to Reid, (2003) people with reading and writing problems have a great deal to offer society through their creativity, skills and talents which always lie dormant and untapped due to frustration of not being able to read fluently and write like the rest. A friendly environment and appropriate instructional support should open ways for those who may have experienced failure in their school life. Pupils have different ways of learning and hence have different strengths and needs. Every pupil with a learning

challenge has his/her own learning style, interests, needs and strengths. Nonetheless, teachers should be able to help the learners through the use of appropriate instructional strategies to identify their strengths and interests in order for them to be able to learn successfully (Shaywitz, 2003). It is also helpful for parents and teachers to make the pupils aware of their learning difficulty and ability so that the pupil can have a positive self-image which help in building a successful and competent person. Teachers should therefore give the parents and pupils examples of successful people who had reading and writing problem in school (Shaywitz, 2003).

Reading is a very important skill that must be acquired by learners. It will help them in understanding the meaning of text learnt in the school. Also, it is an important skill in day to day life of humans. Cahyanni (2007), sees reading as a means of bringing meaning to and getting meaning from printed or written materials. Based on the above, it can be concluded that reading is an active process or a process to understanding meaning, message and purpose from printed or written material that connects reader to writer's idea.

According to Geilet (1984) the following process of reading will be discussed below; skimming, scanning, extensive, reading and intensive reading: Skimming is reading quickly by running one's eyes over a text to get the gist of it. The activities included in this way are compare value, find and compare events, set a title, draw inferences, decide the question, and create the title. Scanning on its part, is reading quickly through a text to find a particular piece of information. The activities included in this way are words for old, locate grammar features, find specified advertisement, compare details, check dates, shopping list, make words sets, and newspaper headlines. Extensive reading is reading longer text, usually for one's own pleasure. The activities dealing with it are stretching overall meaning, information, and general understanding, for example reading short stories, fiction, novel, book.

On the other hand, intensive reading is reading shorter text to extract specific information. It occurs when pupils focus on the language rather than the text. The activities that are found in this way are finding main idea, making inferences, identifying words that connect one idea to another, for example reading newspaper, magazine, identifying grammar on the text. According to Dewi (2013), the importance of reading is multidimensional. Below are the dimensions of reading:

Reading is an Active Mental Process. When reading, children would be forced to think about things not yet known. In this process, pupils would find out information that would build pupils' critical thinking. Improving children's vocabulary is very important. By reading, children can learn new words and the meaning (as yet unknown) to read and understand the content of a text. Pupils need to focus and concentrate on books or texts that are being read for a long time. Unlike magazines, internet or email that only contains small pieces of information, a book would tell a whole story. Therefore, it is necessary concentrating to read so that the concentration of the children will be better.

Furthermore, building self-confidence is also an essential factor. The more someone reads, the more knowledge is gained. Increasing knowledge will further build confidence in children living with Dyslexia. It is a chain reaction, many studies have equally shown that if one does not use the memory, the memory can be lost. Reading is one of the activities that train the memory. Reading helps to stretch the memory because reading requires memory to detail facts and figures on a piece of literature, plot, theme, or character of the story. Reading will make someone's memory increase. Moreover, improved discipline concerns adding books as other sources as written texts in reading activities into children's daily schedule and stick to the schedule with improved discipline. Finally, increasing creativity reading about the diversity of life and being open to the ideas, and the new information will help the development of children's creative side of the brain.

Acquisition of reading competencies and Competency Testing in Primary Education System

The ability to read opens avenues for self-exploration and self-enrichment that would otherwise be inaccessible (Marshall, 2000). Further, reading permits individuals to deepen their understanding of other critical domains of knowledge and allows them to experience feelings of pleasure, beauty, excitement, and more (Reed & Schallert, 1993; Wade & Moje, 2000). Given the essential nature of reading, it is understandable why so much attention has been directed towards this fundamental ability now and in years past. The ability to survive and to thrive in our world is strongly linked to achieving competence as a reader. For that reason, educators, parents and the general public must do what they can to ensure that theirs is a literate society; a society of competent readers, as well as competent writers, speakers, and listeners. To achieve the goals, inclusion in education must be well implemented as even children who find it difficult to read are encouraged to acquire basic skills in reading before becoming adults.

If this goal of a literate society is to be achieved, we must take another look at what it means to read competently. We must consider what it takes to read well not just in the early years, as children struggle to unravel the mysteries and beauty of written and spoken language, but across the lifespan, as the purposes for reading and the character of written language change. In other words, we can do more to realize the goal of a literate society, if we better understand the full nature of reading development.

Within the literacy community, there are two distinct but complementary perspectives on reading development and acquiring reading competencies. The first perspective, prevalent in several well publicized documents and federal legislation (e.g., Snow, Burns, & Griffin, 1998), deals almost exclusively with the early period of reading development that is, the early stages of acquiring reading skills, what might be described as emergent literacy. This early period is unquestionably a critical time in the process of acquiring reading competence, and there are virtually libraries devoted to basic dimensions of reading acquisition, including phonological awareness, vocabulary, and fluency (Adams, 1990; National Reading Panel, 2000) Yet, there is another view of reading development that extends well beyond the initial period of basic skill and process acquisition.

This perspective looks at reading as “a long-term developmental process,” at the end of which “the proficient adult reader can read a variety of materials with ease and interest, can read for varying purposes, and can read with comprehension even when the material is neither easy to understand nor intrinsically interesting” (RAND Reading Study Group, 2002, p. xiii). This particular orientation does not discount the emergent literacy view, but subsumes it as a first step in lifespan development. It is this second perspective of reading development—one less addressed in public and political rhetoric, legislation, and educational policies—that we examine here. Specifically, it is the goal to investigate how reading develops across the lifespan by building on the vast literatures in developmental psychology, cognitive psychology, expertise, motivation, and domain-specific learning, as well as reading research. There are important educational benefits accrued by viewing reading within such a lifespan developmental framework. For one, it helps us to consider the changes and challenges students and adults face once they journey beyond the early elementary grades. Currently, there is an increased awareness that more must be done to understand the nature of adolescent literacy.

According to Sav Keo (2017), to progress through the education process, pupils must achieve certain competency levels. These levels determine what skills and concepts an individual possesses in a certain subject, and if they are suitable to move onto higher level. Reading and writing competencies are often gauged using tests that differ depending on the age and basic knowledge of the subject.

Reading comprehension is the level of understanding a subject has achieved with regard to a written text. Reading comprehension works together with writing comprehension as the two subjects work simultaneously with each other. Proficient reading competency includes the ability to quickly recognize, and analyze words as well understand them. Cognitive concepts are a significant part in reading competency as it allows for an expansion of terms in one’s dialect, and it assists with word and sound association (Sav Keo, 2017).

According, to Tefera.T. (2017), reading skill refers to the ability to understand written text. It is advisable to develop this skill in children at an early age of schooling, especially those with dyslexia. When pupils comprehend or understand written text, and combine their understanding with prior knowledge, they are able to perform the following three reading comprehension tasks: identify simple facts presented in written text (literal comprehension), make judgments about the written text’s content (evaluative comprehension) connect the text to other written passages and situations (inferential comprehension).

The development of these reading skills is vital to children’s development, and a sheer volume of studies have demonstrated a link between competency in reading and overall attainment in school. According to OCFD’s report on reading for change, program for international pupils’ assessment, (PISA,) “Reading for pleasure is more important for children’s educational success than their family’s socioeconomic status to a point, even though socioeconomic status is also very important as provision of books is easier. Besides, there are some other key benefits of engaging children in reading from the early age. This is so because the development of reading is a key to future success both in school and in life. By supporting children with dyslexia to read in their leisure time at every age, parents can help to ensure that children are equipped with the necessary skills to succeed in later life.

Effective Parental Involvement, Practices in Promoting Pupils Reading Competencies

Educators, parents, and community members may have different opinions regarding effective involvement practices, and the ways each can contribute to the educational process of pupils. Parental involvement in the education of pupils begins at home with the parents providing a safe and healthy environment, appropriate learning experiences, support (provision of needs), and a positive attitude about school. According to Epstein (2000), there is increased reading competencies with pupils who have involved parents. He views it as a partnership between educators and parents.

By examining parents’ and teachers’ perceptions, educators and parents should have a better understanding of effective parental involvement practices in promoting pupil’s achievement. The Michigan State Government notes that parental involvement is one of the most important deciding factors in a child’s acquisition of reading competencies, and suggests that the earlier a parent can intercede with a child’s education, the more successful this child will ultimately be (Epstein, 2000).

Supporting Home reading for Children with Dyslexia

Supporting services, otherwise known as related services, are usually alongside special education programmes to enable children with special needs carry out some benefit from the training they receive at school. Many pupils, according to Meyen (1996), need supporting services provided by parents so that they can participate in instructional programmes. With the trend towards serving more pupils with disabilities in regular classes (inclusive class rooms), there has emerged a greater urge for increased instructional support services. Thus, related services have hitherto been offered to complement special education programmes in regular school classes. Without these services, majority of pupil's served by special education would not benefit from instruction they received. For example, special language therapy (service) may improve a pupil communication permitting greater communication performance and participation in a wider range of educational opportunities. So, closely linked are related services to special education programmes that the personnel involved in these services delivery also participate in programme planning for pupils with learning disabilities (Meyen, 1996).

According to Wood (1993), related services or supported services are those services that are needed to assist a child with disability to benefit from regular education. This explanation sees the concept as services that are offered in addition to special education programmes to facilitate learning. Lewis & Doorlag (1995), see supported services as services offered to pupils with disabilities to supplement special education programmes.

Related services and private additional support services for children with dyslexia

These services include transportation and other corrections, and supportive services such as psychological services, counseling, home teacher provision, recreational and diagnostic medical services (Meyen, 1996). According to Leslie & Allen (1999), parents can promote pupil's reading competencies especially in children with dyslexia. This has to do with small group literacy instruction after school where parents read to their children. The time spent on reading connected text is found to be strongly associated with reading growth. This includes independent reading at home. Recreational reading is also found to be positively associated with reading gains as it helps increase pupil's motivation to read.

Lilly (2003), further supports the concept of supporting home reading for children by elaborating on eight enabling conditions for early literacy development at home and school. These enabling conditions are immersion about which he states that high quality children's books and other print could be available around pupils. Engagement: Children could also be encouraged to read and write, allowing them to experiment with language and literacy.

Expectation: Parents could set realistic expectations in accordance with the different developmental stages of literacy. Responsibility: Parents could also make the children to take responsibility in selecting books that could make them early accessible. Approximation: Parents and teachers should encourage children when they try, even if they make mistakes; accuracy can follow later. Parents should also encourage the use of oral and written language. Lastly listening and responding to children's use of language should be done by parents and teachers.

Epstein (2009), talks of six important factors with regard to parental involvement. This framework is based on what factors are most effective with regard to children's reading competencies and education. These six factors are parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making and collaborating with the community. They are elaborated on as follows. An active literacy environment could be created by reading aloud, playing word games, story-telling, and demonstrative activities. Adults could demonstrate model reading and writing.

Parenting and promoting Reading in children

Parenting means all of the activities that parents engage into to raise happy and healthy children who become capable pupils. Unlike teachers, whose influence on a child is relatively limited, parents maintain a life-long commitment to their children. Activities that support this type of involvement provide information to parents about their child's development, health, safety, or home conditions that can support pupil's learning. Also included to these are parents' education and other courses or training for parents, family support programmes to assist families with health, nutrition, and other services, home visits at transition points to elementary, middle, and secondary school (Epstein, 2009).

Different Ways Parents can use to Promote Reading Competencies in Children Living with Dyslexia

Communication: This is another way parent can help promote reading competencies in children living with dyslexia. Families and schools communicate with each other in multiple ways. Schools send home notes and flyers about important events and activities. Parents give teachers information about their child's health and educational history. A school website is an additional mode of communication with parents and families, which give conferences with every parent at least once a year, language translators to assist families as needed, regular schedule of useful notices, memos, phone calls, newsletters, and other communications facilities (Epstein, 2009).

Parents can volunteer: This applies to recruiting and organizing help and support from parents for school programs and pupils' activities. Epstein (2009), talked of three basic ways that individuals can volunteer in the education of children as follows. Firstly, parents may volunteer in the school or classroom by helping teachers and administrators as tutors or assistants. Secondly, they may volunteer for the school; for instance, fundraising for an event or promoting a school in the community. Finally, they may volunteer as members of an audience, attending school programmes or performances. This includes: school/classroom volunteer programmes to help teachers, administrators, students, and other parents, parent room or family center for volunteer work, meetings, and resources for families, annual postcard survey to identify all available talents, time, and location of volunteers (Epstein, 2009)

Learning at home: This is another way that parents can use to promote reading competencies in children living with dyslexia. This pertains to providing ideas and information to parents about how they can best assist their children with homework and curricular-related decisions and activities. Parents helping their children with homework or taking them to a museum, are examples of this type of involvement. These activities produce a school-oriented family and encourage parents to interact with the school curriculum. Activities to encourage learning at home provide parents with information on what children are doing in the classroom, and how to help them with homework. These activities are information for families on skills required for pupils in all subjects at each grade, information on homework policies, and how to monitor and discuss schoolwork at home, as well as family participation in setting student goals each year, and in planning for college or work (Epstein, 2009).

Parents involving in Decision Making in School: Parents can promote reading competencies in children living with dyslexia by being involved in decision making in school. This refers to including parents in decision making, and developing parent leaders and representatives. Parents participate in decision making when they become part of school governance committees or join organizations, such as the parent/ teachers association. Other decision-making activities are taking on leadership roles that involve disseminating information to other parents, active PTA or other parent organizations, social warfare or committees for parent leadership and participation, independent advocacy groups to lobby for school reform and improvements, and networks to link all families with parent representatives (Epstein, 2009).

Collaborating with Community: Another way parents can use to promote reading competencies in children living with dyslexia is by collaborating with the community. These pertain to identifying and integrating community services and resources to support and strengthen schools, pupils, and their families. Such collaboration involves providing information for pupils and families on community health, cultural, recreational, social support, and other programs/services, information on community activities that link to learning skills and talents, not leaving summer programmes for pupils. Each of the above factors can lead to various results for pupils, parents, teaching practices, and the school climate (Epstein, 2009).

According to Henderson & Berla (1994), parents also gain a more positive attitude towards the school and its staff, and gain more confidence in assisting their children with homework, by being involved with their education. In addition, they are more likely to gather support for the school and its programs in the community and become more active community members. For teachers, the benefits may be presumed to be better communication with parents, a deeper understanding of the family of their students and their situation, and more effective communication with both the homes and the community (Epstein, 2009).

Henderson and Berla (1994), also claim that the schools should benefit from parental involvement by improved teacher morale, more support from families and higher pupil's academic achievement. In support, Clarke (2007), asserts that Schools function best when parents and the community are active participants and have a sense of ownership of the school. Therefore, it is safe to say that those six factors not only benefit the pupils, but also their parents, teachers and schools.

Parent/Teacher Cooperation and Acquisition of Reading Competence by Children Living with Dyslexia

A related study was conducted in the United Kingdom by Desforges and Boucher (2003), highlighting how parent-school relationship promotes learning performance for learners from ethnic minority groups. According to the reports, majority of these schools listened to parents' concerns, and worked in partnership to resolve any issues or differences that came with learning. These actions prompted parents to base their understanding of their child's academic development on the discussions, interactions and communications shared with school. Likewise, Katyal and Evers (2007) saw proper home-school communication and collaboration as vital for pupils' academic success. They maintained that, collecting information about students in an organized manner cum continuous interaction between the home and the school and was a modern technology for promoting learning outside the classroom environment. Kaytal and Evers (2007), also concluded that communication as a tool played an important role and served as the bedrock for home – school partnerships. Studies from the United States showed that the effect size, which assesses the level of changes brought about by interventions of PI on children's school success was. 51 for all schools (Hattie,2009) and from .70 to .74 for

primary schools located in urban areas (Jeynes, 2005). Also, Hattie (2009) reported that the size of intervention in education was recorded at 4. This implied that any figures above this percentage on parents' involvement would definitely influence children's academic performance.

Additionally, when there was positive collaboration and partnership between school and families, children achieved much higher in academics, and increased in the time spent in school (Barton and Coley, 2007; Reynolds and Clement, 2005). Schools that promoted family collaboration developed high level improvement in classroom tasks, teacher morale, social skills and high community rating compared to schools that never supported partnership with parents, or engaged them in school activities. Evidence from last thirty years of educating learners with disabilities lends more credence to this by emphasizing the significance of parent participation in learner's school achievement. Research showed that parental expectations, school and family behaviors affected pupils' academic performance and learning outcomes respectively (Redding, 2002; Epstein, 2001). For example, Grolnick and Slowiaczek (1994) measured a theorized three-dimensional interpretation of PI comprising the social, mental and parental aspects.

Azah (2016) carried out research on the effect of differentiated instruction on the fluency and decoding skills of children with English Language reading problems: A Case Study of Primary Four Pupils of Government School Bukwai Cameroon. A quasi experimental research design was used for this study. Both purposive and random sampling techniques were used for the study. Vygotsky's Social Constructivist theory was used for the research. According to the result gotten, comparing between the experimental and the control group, though there was an increase in the difference in favour of the experimental group, this difference was not significant (Mann Whitney U test: $P > 0.05$).

The result of this study revealed that the post-test scores were better than the pre-test scores. It could be seen by comparing their means. The mean of the pre-test scores was 11.18 while the mean of the post-test scores was 19.25. The difference between the two means was 8.56. The result of applying one sample test revealed that the obtained value (15.03) was higher than the t-table value (2.02). It means that there was significant difference in grade of speaking test achieved by the students after they have been taught using Audio-lingual Teaching Method and effective method. Although the study focused on class four pupils, many primary school children have fundamental learning gaps in the acquisition of reading skills and they actually go through primary school and complete without learning how to read fluently and accurately.

This empirical review is very relevant to the present study because it clearly brought out how parent-school relationship promotes learning performance for learners from ethnic minority groups. Parental cooperation with teachers is capable of bringing out positive reading acquisition and academic success. This study brought out the fact that parent-school cooperation promotes the learning performance of learners from ethnic minority groups. But this research was carried for ethnic minority groups. The researcher is willing to fill in the gap by conducting similar research on dyslexic children. Also, the researcher is going to carry out similar research to show how parent-school relationships promote reading competencies in children.

Suryani (2012) conducted a study aimed at describing the implementation of effective communication and Audio-Lingual Methods in teaching English at the fourth year of SDN Bedoro 2 Sambungmacan Sragen. The objectives of this research paper were to describe: (1) the implementation of Audio-Lingual Method in teaching English especially at the fourth year of SDN Bedoro 2 Sambungmacan Sragen, (2) the problems faced by the teacher and the solution in teaching English using Audio Lingual Method. The type of this research was descriptive qualitative research. The subject of this research was English teacher and the fourth-grade students of SDN Bedoro 2 Sambungmacan. The object of this research was teaching-learning process of English by using Audio Lingual and effective communication methods. The research used descriptive method as method of collecting data in this study by employing observation, interview, and document. The researcher got the data of this research from field note, observation, and interview. The result of the analysis showed that the goals of teaching English by using Audio Lingual and effective communication methods were that the students were more active in the word and sentences repetition drilling. This researcher employed purely a qualitative approach and there is need to confirm or disconfirm the results using quantitative approach. Moreover, the study focused more on language learning of children through teachers but failed to examine the part played by parents in language acquisition and competences

This empirical review broadens the understanding to know the extent to which school, family, and community partnerships helps in the reading achievement of children. It also provides knowledge on the different parental involvement activities that can significantly influence the reading competency of children. But the study was conducted on African-American Male fourth grade pupils. The researcher is willing to fill the gap by conducting a similar research on dyslexic children in the southwest region of Cameroon to show that parental involvement significantly influences the reading achievement of children with dyslexia.

Dewi (2010) conducted a study on the effects of total physical response and direct teaching methods storytelling to teach vocabulary to improve elementary students' vocabulary achievement. This study was conducted to find out the effectiveness of total physical response-and direct teaching methods storytelling to teach vocabulary to improve elementary students' vocabulary achievement. It was a quasi-experimental study. The research instrument in this study was the vocabulary test that consisted of 50 multiple-choice items that the students had to finish in 90 minutes. Then, she set the level of significance which was 0.05. Finally, she analyzed the data by using Mann Whitney U Test. From the results of the research, it showed that Total Physical Response-Story Telling (TPR-S) and direct teaching method gave significant influence to improve students' vocabulary development. The students who were taught by using Total Physical Response-Story Telling (TPR-S) and direct teaching method obtained higher vocabulary achievement than those who were taught by using translation. The researcher focused his study only on vocabulary neglecting all other reading indicators and agents that facilitate reading acquisition like the parents.

Theoretical Framework

The Theory of Language Acquisition by Noam Chomsky (1981)

Language is a system of conventional spoken, manual, or written symbols by means of which human beings, as members of a social group and participants in its culture, express themselves. The function of language includes communication, the expression of identity, play, imaginative expression and emotional release.

Chomsky's government-binding theory (1981) says that a child's native knowledge of syntax consists of a group of linguistic principles that define the form of any language. These principles are connected with parameters triggered by the child's language environment. Chomsky emphasizes the importance of the child's genetic inheritance of the syntax imprint. For Chomsky, the "growth" of language is analogous to the growth of internal organs, arms and legs -- determined by internal mechanisms, but nourished by the environment -- whether verbal or nutritional. Chomsky sees language development in the child as a separate aspect of knowledge, apart from the rest of cognition, or mental functioning.

Chomsky also says that knowing a language is synonymous with the capacity to produce an infinite number of sentences never previously spoken, and to understand sentences never before heard. This ability is what Chomsky calls the "creative aspect" of language. Understanding the mechanics of language elucidates patterns of human thought, and places linguistics within the realm of psychology. Evidence that children are born with an understanding of syntax is the ease and facility with which they learn language, according to Chomsky. Noam Chomsky published a criticism of the behaviourist theory in 1957. He focused particularly on the impoverished language input children receive. Adults do not typically speak in grammatically complete sentences. In addition, what the child hears is only a small sample of language.

Chomsky concluded that children must have an inborn faculty for language acquisition. According to this theory, the process is biologically determined - the human species have evolved a brain whose neural circuits contain linguistic information at birth. The child's natural predisposition to learn language is triggered by hearing speech and the child's brain is able to interpret what he/she hears according to the underlying principles or structures it already contains. This natural faculty has become known as the Language Acquisition Device (LAD). ,

Chomsky did not suggest that an English child is born knowing anything specific about English, of course. He stated that all human languages share common principles. (For example, they all have words for things and actions - nouns and verbs.) It is the child's task to establish how the specific language he/she hears expresses these underlying principles. For example, the LAD already contains the concept of verb tense. By listening to such forms as "worked", "played" and "patted", the child will form the hypothesis that the past tense of verbs is formed by adding the sound /d/, /t/ or /id/ to the base form. This, in turn, will lead to the "virtuous errors" mentioned above. It hardly needs saying that the process is unconscious. Chomsky does not envisage the small child lying in its cot working out grammatical rules consciously!

Chomsky's ground-breaking theory remains at the centre of the debate about language acquisition. However, it has been modified, both by Chomsky himself and by others. Chomsky's original position was that the LAD contained specific knowledge about language. Dan Isaac Slobin (2008) has proposed that it may be more like a mechanism for working out the rules of language: "It seems to me that the child is born not with a set of linguistic categories but with some sort of process mechanism - a set of procedures and inference rules, if you wish- that he uses to process linguistic data. These mechanisms are such that, applying them to the input data, the child ends up with something which is a member of the class of human languages. The linguistic universals, then, are the *result* of an innate cognitive competence rather than the content of such a competence." (Russell, 2001).

Evidence to support Chomsky's theory of language acquisition theory

Work in several areas of language study has provided support for the idea of an innate language faculty. Three types of evidence are offered here: Slobin (2008) pointed out that human anatomy is peculiarly adapted to the production of speech. Unlike our nearest relatives, the great apes, humans have evolved a vocal tract which allows the precise articulation of a wide repertoire of vocal sounds. Neuro-science has also identified specific areas of the brain with distinctly linguistic functions, notably Broca's area and Wernicke's area. Stroke victims provide valuable data: depending on the site of brain damage; they may suffer a range of language dysfunction, from problems with finding words to an inability to interpret syntax. Experiments aimed at teaching chimpanzees to communicate using plastic symbols or manual gestures have proved controversial. It seems likely that our ape cousins, while able to learn individual "words", have little or no grammatical competence. Pinker (1994) offers a good account of this research.

The formation of creole varieties of English appears to be the result of the LAD at work. The linguist Derek Bickerton has studied the formation of Dutch-based creoles in Surinam. Escaped slaves, living together but originally from different language groups, were forced to communicate in their very limited Dutch. The result was the restricted form of language known as a pidgin. The adult speakers were past the critical age at which they could learn a new language fluently - they had learned Dutch as a foreign language and under unfavorable conditions. Remarkably, the children of these slaves turned the pidgin into a full language, known by linguists as a creole. They were presumably unaware of the process but the outcome was a language variety which follows its own consistent rules and has a full expressive range. Creoles based on English are also found in the Caribbean Islands and elsewhere.

Research Methods

Research Design

This study employed a mixed methodology, involving both quantitative and qualitative methods. To enable the reader, have a broad knowledge of the concept under investigation. To compare the responses from the two correspondences. A mixed research design was used specifically quasi- experimental design (a one group pretest posttest design) was used on a sample of 5 participants. the (quantitative study comes before a qualitative study) to have a broader understanding of the concepts under investigation, to compare responses from the respondents. The researcher conducted a survey using questionnaire and also a one group pretest posttest quasi experimental. Interviews were also conducted. The one group pretest and posttest design had no comparison group and utilizes only a pretest posttest to see programme or intervention effects. This design is generally used to test the extent to which a particular programme initially proven inefficient could impact in a different context after effective orientation. The design is also relevant to this study because it is intervening research and it could only be this design as it will give the right result after treatment and easy to measure through pupils' performance. This is of great importance to this study as it enables us have a brother understand of the concepts investigated in the study, to compare the responses from the correspondence.

Sample Population

The sample of this study was limited to classes four and five pupils in one private, one public and one mission schools in the three Municipalities that is Buea, Limbe and Tiko in the South-West Region thus making a total of nine schools. Fako Division has a total of about 110 primary schools with a pupil population of 30342. It has a teacher population of 1399 for the 2018-2019 academic years. This study used a sample of nine schools from Buea, Limbe and Tiko Divisions.

Pupils are used for this study because they are the ones that can give an accurate measure of parental involvement in their reading skills. Their responses tell us about parents' activities, their commitment, and difficulties faced. The pupil population was limited to Classes Four and Five because they can provide the researcher with the necessary information for this study. They are mature enough to understand questions, and respond to questions. In addition, they are in those classes where reading competency is easily fostered by teachers and parents through home and school activities.

Teachers were also part of the population under study because the study focuses on impact of teacher and parent relationship concerning children with dyslexia. As such their opinion was very important. Teachers' population was limited to teachers who teach these pupils in Classes Four and Five. Parents were included in this study because they are the caretakers of these pupils and are the ones who assist them in their homework. They work with the children every day. As such, they can provide the necessary information needed for the study.

Sampling Technique

In this study the purposive sampling technique was used where pupils with dyslexia were identified in the purposive schools(GPS Down Beach, Presbyterian Primary School Limbe, Ibolykaszabo Foundation, GS Likoko Membea, Catholic School Molyko, Potter's House Buea, GS Mudeka, Divine Faith Mutenguenue and CBC Bakingili with classes four and five pupils of the same schools) From this cohort of pupils a proper assessment was done by the researcher to confirm the presence of dyslexia in the pupils identified by the teacher. Through the pupils the researcher got to the parents as each child was able to give the mother or fathers number to the researcher. The researcher then gave a pretest to the pupils to

see their level in reading competences. The types of pretests given were as follows: productive assessment test, word recognition assessment test, decoding test, automatic naming test and a standardized assessment which results were obtain and very low. The above tests were also done at the end of the exercise to see if the intervening research worked. The researcher liaised with the 5 pupils to their parents.

Findings

Parental Cooperation with Teachers Towards Children Living with Dyslexia and Children's Acquisition of Reading Competency?

Pupils' perspectives

Table 1: Pupils' Characterization of Parental Cooperation with Teachers at Pre-Test

Items	Stretched				Collapsed	
	SA	A	D	SD	SA & A	D & SD
My parents always attend P.T.A meetings in my schools.	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	20.0% (1)	80.0% (4)	0.0% (0)	100% (5)
My parents always speak with my class teacher concerning my performance.	0.0% (0)	40.0% (2)	20.0% (1)	40.0% (2)	40% (2)	80% (4)
My parents visit my school.	0.0% (0)	80.0% (4)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	80% (4)	20% (1)
My parents often ask me what I learn in school.	0.0% (0)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	60.0% (3)	20% (1)	60% (3)
My parents often help me in my home work	0.0% (0)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	80.0% (4)	20% (1)	80% (4)
My parents often attend my individualized education plan meeting.	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	20.0% (1)	80.0% (4)	0.0% (0)	100% (5)
MRS	0.0% (0)	26.7% (8)	16.7% (5)	56.7% (17)	26.7% (8)	73.3% (22)

Pupils at pretest for the majority were not satisfied with parental cooperation with teachers, with weight of 73.3%, following the questionnaire on the items "my parents always attend PTA meetings in my school" and "my parents often help me in my home work with a 100% strongly agree and agree and a frequency of 5. Following the questionnaire item my parents always speak with my class teacher concerning my performance, the respondents had 80% strongly disagreed and disagreed with a frequency of 4, and 40% of the respondents strongly agree and agree with a frequency of 2. Concerning the item, "my parents visit my school" had 80% strongly agree, and agree and a frequency of 4 and 20% strongly disagree and disagree with a frequency of 1. Again, on the item "my parent often asks me what I learn in school" had 60% strongly disagree and disagree with a frequency of 3 and 20% strongly agree and agree with a frequency of 1. To Rocks and the author(s) Copyright (2018), by highlighting a struggling child's capabilities and talents, you not only help professionals, that is, teachers know your child as a whole person, you can also assist in identifying learning accommodations of your dyslexic child, visit the school, and ask what he or she has done.

Table 2: Pupils' Characterization of Parental Cooperation with Teachers at Posttest

Items	SA	A	D	SD	SA & A	D & SD
My parents always attend P.T.A meetings in my schools.	60.0% (3)	40.0% (2)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100% (5)	0.0% (0)
My parents always speak with my class teacher concerning my performance.	80.0% (4)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100% (5)	0.0% (0)
My parents visit my school.	20.0% (1)	60.0% (3)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	80% (4)	20% (1)
My parents often ask me what I learn in school.	40.0% (2)	40.0% (2)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	80% (4)	20% (1)

My parents often help me in my home work	20.0% (1)	60.0% (3)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	80% (4)	20% (1)
My parents often attend my individualized education plan meeting.	0.0% (0)	80.0% (4)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	80% (4)	20% (1)
MRS	23.3% (7)	60.0% (18)	16.7% (5)	0.0% (0)	83.3% (25)	16.7% (5)

From table 2, pupils at posttest for the majority were not satisfied with parental cooperation with teachers, with weight of 83.3%. Following the items in the questionnaire “my parents always attend P TA meetings in my school”, strongly agree and agree had 100% (5), while strongly disagree and disagree had 0.0%. “My parents always speak with my class teacher concerning my performance” had 80% strongly agree and agree and 20% agree making a total of 100% (5). My parents visit my school had 80% strongly agree and agree with 80%strongly agreed and agree. My parent often asks me what I learn in school had a percentage of 80% strongly agreed and agree with 20% strongly disagree and disagree and a frequency of 1. On the questionnaire my parents often help me in my homework the respondents had 80% (4) strongly agree and agree. My parents often attend my individualized education plan meeting had 80% (4) strongly agree and agree while strongly disagree and disagree had 20% (1)

Figure 1: Pupils’ Characterization of Parental Cooperation with Teachers Comparing between Pretest and Post-Test

At pretest, the proportion of children that were satisfied with parental cooperation with teacher were 26.7%, and this proportion rose significantly to 83.3% at posttest ($P < 0.05$).

Table 3: Correlation between Parental Affection and Acquisition of Reading Competencies Based on Pupils’ Perceptions

		Performance In Reading	
Pearson	Cooperation with teachers	Correlation Coefficient	.816*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.004
		N	10

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

There was a very significant and positive correlation between parental cooperation with teachers and performance in reading of pupils with dyslexia ($R = 0.816$; $P = 0.004$). This therefore implies that the better parents cooperate with teachers, the more the likelihood for children with dyslexia to do well in reading.

Parents' perspectives

Table 4: Parents' Characterization of Parental Cooperation with Teachers at Pre-Test

Items	Stretched				Collapsed	
	SA	A	D	SD	SA & A	D & SD
I attend P.T.A meetings in my child's school in order to know what is going on there.	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100.0% (5)	0.0% (0)	100% (5)
I communicate with the teacher of my child concerning my child's performance	0.0% (0)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	80.0% (4)	20% (1)	80% (4)
I visit my child's school, and I maintain a good relationship with his/her teacher	0.0% (0)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	80.0% (4)	20% (1)	80% (4)
I talk to my children about what they learn in school	0.0% (0)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	80.0% (4)	20% (1)	80% (4)
I help or supervise my children to do their homework / assignment	0.0% (0)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	80.0% (4)	20% (1)	80% (4)
I work with my child at home especially on subjects he's not good in like reading and writing.	0.0% (0)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	80.0% (4)	20% (1)	80% (4)
MRS	0.0% (0)	16.7% (5)	0.0% (0)	83.3% (25)	16.7% (5)	83.3% (25)

Parents at pretest generally perceived that they were not cooperating with teachers with weight of 76.7%. From the questionnaire them "I attend P T A meetings in my child's school in order to know what is going on there", the respondents had 100% (5) strongly disagree and disagree, "I communicate with the teacher of my child concerning my child's performance", the respondents had 80% (4) strongly disagree and disagree while strongly agree and agree had 20%. I visit my child's school and maintain a good relationship with his or her teacher had 80% strongly disagree and disagree with a 20% strongly agree and agree. I talk to my children about what they learn in school, had a percentage of 80% (4) strongly disagree and disagree. Following the questionnaire, I help supervise my children to do their homework especially on subjects he or she is not good in like reading and writing, the respondents had a percentage of 80% (4) strongly disagree and disagree and 20% strongly agree and agree. According to Mbua (2001), parent's cooperation with their dyslexic children's teacher has a great role to play in the acquisition of reading competencies in schools. With the help of parent teachers, association school functional system and pupil's performance in school will solely depend on effective parent teacher's cooperation, which provide all the basic school needs for a dyslexic child to study.

Table 5: Parents' characterization of parental cooperation with teachers at post-test

Items	SA	A	D	SD	SA & A	D & SD
I attend P.T.A meetings in my child's school in order to know what is going on there.	80.0% (4)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100% (5)	0.0% (0)
I communicate with the teacher of my child concerning my child's performance	60.0% (3)	40.0% (2)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100% (5)	0.0% (0)
I visit my child's school, and I maintain a good relationship with his/her teacher	40.0% (2)	60.0% (3)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100% (5)	0.0% (0)
I talk to my children about what they learn in school	60.0% (3)	40.0% (2)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100% (5)	0.0% (0)
I help or supervise my children to do their homework / assignment	80.0% (4)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100% (5)	0.0% (0)
I work with my child at home especially on subjects he's not good in like reading and writing.	20.0% (1)	60.0% (3)	20.0% (1)	0.0% (0)	80% (4)	20% (1)
MRS	55.7% (17)	40.0% (12)	3.3% (1)	0.0% (0)	96.7% (29)	3.3% (1)

Parents at posttest generally perceived that they were cooperating with teachers with weight of 96.7%. A post-test following the questionnaire I attend P.T.A meetings in my child's school in order to know what is going on there, their, communicate with the teacher of my child concerning their child performance, I visit my child's school, and I maintain a

good relationship with his or her teacher, I talk to my children about what they learn in school and I help or supervise my children to do their homework or assignment, all of these respondents had a percentage of 100% (4) strongly agree and agree. Following the item, I work with my child at home especially on subjects he is not good in like reading and writing, the respondents had a percentage of 80% (4) strongly agree and agree with a 20% strongly disagree and disagree. To Harris and Goodall (2007), effective parent- teacher cooperation such as communicating with the teacher of their children concerning their academic performance, by visiting the school of their dyslexic children and maintaining a good relationship with his or her teacher, this greatly influence children acquisition of competencies in the area of reading.

Figure 2 : Parents’ Characterization of Parental Cooperation with Teachers Comparing Between Pretest and Post-Test

At pretest, the proportion of parents that were satisfied with their cooperation with teacher were 16.7%, and this proportion rose significantly to 96.7% at posttest ($P < 0.05$).

Table 6: Correlation between Parental Affection and Acquisition of Reading Competencies Based on Pupils’ Perceptions

		Performance in reading	
Pearson	Cooperation with teachers	Correlation Coefficient	.716*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.020
		N	10

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

There was a very significant and positive correlation between parental cooperation with teachers and performance in reading of pupils with dyslexia ($R = 0.716$; $P = 0.020$). This therefore implies that the better parents cooperate with teachers, the more the likelihood for children with dyslexia to do well in reading.

Teachers’ perspectives

Table 7: Teachers’ Characterization of Parental Cooperation with Teachers at Pretest

Items	Stretched				Collapsed	
	SA	A	D	SD	SA & A	D & SD
I have the phone contacts of parents of all my pupils.	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100% (3)	0.0% (0)	100% (3)
I always make sure to inform all the parents of my pupils about the P.T.A meetings.	0.0% (0)	33.3% (1)	0.0% (0)	66.7% (2)	33.3% (1)	66.7% (2)
I always inform the parents of my pupils if there are any perceived changes in their children	0.0% (0)	33.3% (1)	0.0% (0)	100% (2)	33.3% (1)	66.7% (2)
I always make sure I discuss with parents of my pupils on their children’s performances.	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100% (3)	0.0% (0)	60.0% (3)
I always make sure I have a good relationship with parents of my pupils.	0.0% (0)	33.3% (1)	0.0% (0)	66.7% (2)	33.3% (1)	66.7% (2)

I stay with, my pupils after school till they are all picked up by their parents or guardians	0.0% (0)	33.3% (1)	0.0% (0)	66.7% (2)	33.3% (1)	66.7% (2)
MRS	0.0% (0)	22.2% (4)	0.0% (0)	77.8% (14)	22.2% (4)	77.8% (14)

Teachers at pretest generally perceived that they were not cooperating with parents with weight of 77.8%. Following the response from the questionnaire, I have the contact number of parents of all my pupils, the response was 100% (3) strongly disagree and disagree. I always make sure to inform all the parents of my pupils about the P T A meetings had a percentage of 66.7% strongly disagree and disagree and 33.3% strongly agree and agree. I always inform the parents of my pupils if they are any changes in their children performance had 66.7% strongly disagree and disagree. Following the item, I always make sure I have a good relationship with parents of my pupils had 66.7% (2) and finally on the item I stay with my pupils after school till they are picked up by their parents or guardians had 66.7% (2) strongly disagree and disagree and 33.3% strongly agree and agree.

Table 8: Teachers’ Characterization of Parental Cooperation with Teachers at Post-Test

Items	SA	A	D	SD	SA & A	D & SD
I have the phone contacts of parents of all my pupils.	0.0% (0)	100% (3)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100% (3)	0.0% (0)
I always make sure to inform all the parents of my pupils about the P.T.A meetings.	0.0% (0)	100% (3)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100% (3)	0.0% (0)
I always inform the parents of my pupils if there are any perceived changes in their children	0.0% (0)	66.7% (2)	33.3% (1)	0.0% (0)	66.7% (2)	33.3% (1)
I always make sure i discuss with parents of my pupils on their children’s performances.	0.0% (0)	66.7% (2)	33.3% (1)	0.0% (0)	66.7% (2)	33.3% (1)
I always make sure I have a good relationship with parents of my pupils.	0.0% (0)	100% (3)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100% (3)	0.0% (0)
I stay with, my pupils after school till they are all picked up by their parents or guardians	0.0% (0)	100% (3)	0.0% (0)	0.0% (0)	100% (3)	0.0% (0)
MRS	0.0% (0)	77.4% (14)	% (0)	% (0)	88.9% (16)	11.1% (2)

Teachers at posttest generally perceived that they were cooperating with parents with weight of 88.9%. All of them agreed that they have the phone contacts of parents of all their pupils was at 100% (3), that they always make sure to inform all the parents of their pupils about the P.T.A meetings 100%. Those that always make sure to have a good relationship with parents of my pupils stood at 100%. Those that stay with their pupils after school till they are all picked up by their parents or guardians was 100% A proportion of 66.7% (2) always inform the parents of their pupils if there are any perceived changes in their children, while the same proportion always make sure they discuss with their parents of their pupils on their children’s performances.

Figure 3: Teachers' Characterization of Parental Cooperation with Teachers Comparing Between Pretest and Post-Test

At pretest, the proportion of teachers that were satisfied with their cooperation with parents were 22.2%, and this proportion rose significantly to 88.9% at posttest ($P < 0.05$).

Table 9: Correlation between Parental Affection and Acquisition of Reading Competencies Based on Teachers' Perceptions

		Performance in reading	
Pearson	Cooperation with parents	Correlation Coefficient	.924**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.008
		N	6

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

There was a very significant and positive correlation between cooperation with parents and performance in reading of pupils with dyslexia ($R=0.924$; $P=0.008$). This therefore implies that the better teachers cooperate with parents, the more the likelihood for children with dyslexia to do well in reading.

Parental Cooperation with Teachers and Children Acquisition of Competencies in Reading

From observation on this hypothesis, it was discovered that parents participate during parent /teacher association but had nothing to do again with the teachers. For them their contribution to their children's education ends at PTA meetings. With the creation of awareness by the researcher in the field it was discovered that many parents responded positively as they discovered a bit of their interest in cooperating with the class teacher increased their children performance in school. Following responses from the interview carried out with parents of dyslexic children, different responses explained that cooperation between them (parents) and teachers plays a role in enhancing their acquisition of reading competences.

Discussions

From the result, it is deduced that there is a significant and positive correlation between parental cooperation with teachers and performance in reading of pupils with dyslexia as many parents agreed that they had the phone numbers of their children's teachers, that they always attend P.T.A meetings in their children's school, that they communicate with the teachers of their children concerning their performance in school, they also accepted that they have a good relationship with the teachers of their children, and supervise their children at home as they do their homework.

The findings also revealed that most pupils were satisfied with the fact that their parents always attend PTA meetings in their school as a good proportion of them agreed that their parents always speak with their class teacher concerning their performance. From observation parents of children with dyslexia need to do more to their children beyond just attending PTA meetings. Parent of children with dyslexia must constantly be in touch with their teachers so as to get the feedback of how the children are performing in school. This was seen as children whose parent often communicate with their teachers perform well in reading more than children whose parent only care about PTA meetings. From interview. Parents were equally positive about parental cooperation with teachers and children acquisition of competencies in reading

These finding were in support of Epstein (2009) six important factors with regards to parental involvement in the education of children. These finding is further supported by Abouochaer (2003) who heighted how parent-school relationship promotes learning performance for learners from ethnic minority groups. According to the report, majority of those schools listened to parents concerns and work in partnership to resolved issues or differences that came with learning. The study continues to illustrated that many parents work with their children at home especially on subjects that they were not good at. This is in conformity with Kaytal &Evers (2007) who said that communication as a tool played an important role and served as bedrock for home-school partnerships.

The study further illustrate that most teachers agreed that they had the phone numbers of their pupil's parents, make sure they informed them about PTA meetings, have good relationship with them and stay with their pupils after school until their parents picked them up. This showed a significant and positive relationship with teachers and pupils' performance in reading. These findings are further supported by Faye Covington Bradley (2010) that parental involvement significantly influences reading achievement of pupils.

Also, these findings are further supported by the Ecological Systems Theory of Bronfenbrenner (1979) which depicts on the developing child and the child's interactions with people, objects and symbols in proximal processes across multiple settings contexts and environments. This theory talks s about the different systems that a child is born into. The researcher finds this theory important to the study because the microsystem which the child is born into can either affect

the child positively or negatively. From observation the children who came from well-cultured homes (microsystem) that correct them with love and encourages them to read performed welling reading more than those that came from families that do not encourage them to read.

Implications for Education and Contributions to Psychological Knowledge

The importance of parental involvement in the acquisition of reading competencies by children with dyslexia has many policy implications. Policy and practice decision makers need to particular attention to parental involvement as their risk children with dyslexia are concerned. They need to find ways to improve parental involvement in the educational achievement of children with dyslexia, taking into consideration factors such as parental affection, parental provision and parental cooperation with teachers of these children.

From the findings, it is glaring that parental involvement in the acquisition of competencies in children living with dyslexia is very important in Cameroon schools. From the findings of this study, it revealed that dyslexia is not known by teachers not to talk of parents who have no knowledge of teaching, so this study will open the eyes of teachers and parents who will be in contact with this piece of work, to know how to handle such children in the classroom and at home. Furthermore, this study is going to improve the level of parent and teacher's cooperation in the area of reading acquisition. This study will make parent and teachers to take the aspect of affection very seriously when it comes to teaching children with dyslexia. From the above findings it observed that poor parental involvement does not only affect children with dyslexia in the area of reading but affect them negatively in other areas of life such as psychologically, and socially (dropping out of school, social misconduct).

Conclusion

In conclusion parent teachers cooperation which employ the relationship that parents have with the teachers of their children such as teachers phone numbers, attending P.T.A meetings, communicating with teachers to know the progress of the child in school, visiting the child's school, talking to the child about what he or she learn in school, helping the child with homework and helping the child at home with difficult subjects shows a significant and positive correlation between parental cooperation with teachers and performance in reading of pupils with dyslexia. This therefore implies that the more parents cooperate with teachers, the more the likelihood for children with dyslexia to do well in reading. The above is in line with Harris and Goodall (2007) that they are many ways in which a school can use in building partnership with the stakeholders and must recognize differences in family orientation and needs.

Suryani (2012) conducted a study aimed at describing the implementation of effective communication and Audio-Lingual Methods in teaching English at the fourth year of SDN Bedoro 2 Sambungmacan Sragen. The result of the analysis showed that the goals of teaching English by using Audio Lingual and effective communication methods were that the students were more active in the word and sentences repetition drilling. This researcher employed purely a qualitative approach and there is need to confirm or disconfirm the results using quantitative approach. Also, the researcher dwelled more on teachers teaching and failed to include parental involvement in the teaching and learning process of reading acquisition.

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